

MODERN TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING LANGUAGES

Togaeva M.A.

Gulistan State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7780508>

Abstract:

This article highlights some effective ways of teaching German as well as some modern educational technologies used in language and learning.

Key words: language , non-language, independent language learning, educational technologies, project, interest, activity, interactive methods.

Today, the focus is on the student, his personality and unique inner world. Therefore, the main task of a modern teacher is the choice of methods and forms of organization of educational activities of students that optimally correspond to the goal of personality development. In recent years, the issue of using new information technologies in schools has been increasingly raised. These are not only new technical means, but also new forms and methods of teaching, a new approach to the educational process. The main goal of teaching foreign languages is the formation and development of the communicative culture of schoolchildren, to teach them to learn a foreign language in practice. In the process of research, popular methods of teaching and learning the German language and Internet resources were used. When writing the article, the principles of theoretical and deductive inference, analysis and synthesis, and logic were used . The task of the teacher is to create conditions for the practical mastery of the language for each student, to enable each student to show their activity and creativity - this is the choice of teaching methods. The task of the teacher is to activate the cognitive activity of the student in the process of teaching foreign languages. Modern pedagogical technologies, such as collaborative learning, project methodology, the use of new information technologies, Internet resources, help to implement a student-centered approach in the educational process, individualization of learning, taking into account the abilities of children, their level of learning, and ensures differentiation. Forms of work with computer training programs in foreign language classes include: learning vocabulary; practice pronunciation; teaching dialogic and monologue speech; learning to write; development of grammatical events.[1]

The possibilities of using Internet resources are enormous. The global Internet provides conditions for students and teachers located anywhere in the world to receive any information they need: regional studies materials, news from the life

of young people, articles from newspapers and magazines, etc. can decide: the formation of reading skills and competence using materials of the global network; improving the writing skills of schoolchildren; replenishment of students' vocabulary; formation of students' motivation to learn the German language. In addition, this work is aimed at exploring the possibilities of Internet technologies for expanding the horizons of schoolchildren, establishing and maintaining business relationships and contacts with peers in German-speaking countries. The main goal of learning a foreign language at school is the formation of communicative competence, all other goals (training, training, development) are realized in the process of realizing this main goal. The communicative approach includes communication training and the formation of intercultural communication skills, which are the basis of Internet activities. Without communication, the Internet does not make sense - it is an international multinational, intercultural society, whose life is based on the electronic communication of millions of people around the world, speaking at the same time - in the number and size of participants. the biggest conversation. By attending foreign language classes for him , we create a real model of communication. Currently, priority is given to communication, interactivity, authenticity of communication, language learning in a cultural context, autonomy and humanitarianism of education. These principles allow the development of intercultural competence as a component of communicative competence. The ultimate goal of teaching foreign languages is to teach free orientation in a foreign language environment and the ability to adequately respond to various situations, i.e. contact Today, new methods using Internet resources are opposed to traditional foreign language teaching. To learn to communicate in a foreign language, it is necessary to create real, life situations that stimulate the assimilation of the material and develop adequate behavior (that is, the so-called principle of communication authenticity). New technologies , especially the Internet, are trying to correct this mistake. The communicative approach is a strategy that imitates communication, aimed at conscious understanding of the material and methods of working with it, creating psychological and linguistic preparation for communication. For the user, it is not particularly difficult to implement a communicative approach on the Internet. The communicative task should encourage students to discuss a problem or issue, students not only exchange information, but also evaluate it . The main criterion for distinguishing this approach from other types of learning activities is the students' independent choice of language units for the formation

of their thoughts. With a communicative approach , the use of the Internet is very well encouraged: its goal is to interest students in learning a foreign language by accumulating and expanding their knowledge and experience. One of the main requirements for teaching foreign languages using Internet resources is interaction in the lesson is to create a riddle that in the methodology is called interactivity. Interactivity is "the unification, coordination and complementation of communicative goals and resultant efforts through speech". By teaching real language , the Internet helps to develop conversational skills and abilities, and also provides genuine interest and, therefore, effectiveness in teaching vocabulary and grammar. Interactivity not only creates real life situations, but also forces students to give appropriate answers to them in a foreign language. One of the technologies that provide student-centered learning is the method of projects as a method of developing creativity, cognitive activity, and independence. The typology of projects is varied. Projects can be divided into mono-projects , collective, oral, concrete, written and Internet projects. In real practice, one often has to deal with research projects, mixed projects that are creative, practice-oriented and informational in nature. Project work is a multifaceted approach to language learning that includes reading, listening, speaking, and grammar. The project method contributes to the development of active independent thinking of students and directs them to joint research work. In my opinion , project-based learning teaches children to cooperate, and learning to cooperate instills moral values such as mutual assistance and empathy, develops creativity and activates students. In general, in project-based learning, there is an inseparability of education and upbringing. The project method develops students' communication skills, a culture of behavior, the ability to concisely and easily form thoughts, tolerantly treat the opinions of communication partners, the ability to receive information from various sources, process using modern computer technologies , creates a language environment conducive to the emergence of natural needs. in communication in a foreign language The project form of work is one of the most relevant technologies that allows students to apply the accumulated knowledge of the subject. [2] Students expand their horizons, the boundaries of language knowledge, gain experience in its practical use, learn to listen and hear speech in a foreign language, understand each other when defending projects. Children work with reference books, dictionaries, computers, and thus create the possibility of direct contact with the real language, which does not ensure the study of the language in the classroom only with the help of textbooks. Project

work is a creative process. The student is looking for a solution to the problem on his own or under the guidance of a teacher, which requires not only knowledge of the language, but also a large amount of subject knowledge, creative, communication and intellectual skills. In a foreign language course, the project method can be used within the program materials of almost any subject. Working on projects develops imagination, fantasy, creative thinking, independence and other personal qualities, modern technologies and cooperation technologies are also applicable. The main idea is to create conditions for the active joint activity of students in different learning conditions. Children are united in groups of 3-4 people, they are given one task, and the role of each is discussed. Each student is responsible not only for the result of his work, but also for the result of the whole group. Therefore, weak students try to learn what they do not understand from weak students, and strong students strive to give weak students a complete understanding of the problem. And the whole class wins because the gaps close together.[3]

Summary:

Information technology in education significantly diversifies the process of perception and processing of information. Thanks to the computer, the Internet and multimedia, a unique opportunity was created for students to absorb a large amount of information with further analysis and sorting. The motivational basis of educational activity is also expanding significantly. In terms of using multimedia, students receive information from newspapers, television, conduct interviews and teleconferences. The main criterion for assessing the level of foreign language proficiency in language portfolio technology is a test. The priority of this technology is the direction of the educational process from teacher to student. The student, in turn, is consciously responsible for the results of their learning activities. The above technology leads to the gradual formation of students' skills of independent assimilation of information. In general, the language portfolio is multifunctional and contributes to the development of multilingualism.

References:

1. Kholdorova M. , Faizieva N., Rikhsittilaeva F. "USE OF NEW INTERACTIVE METHODS IN EDUCATION ABROAD" Tashkent: Nizomi TDPU, 2005
2. O'. Khoshimov, I. Yakubov . "TECHNOLOGY OF TEACHING THE GERMAN LANGUAGE" (textbook) Tashkent: Shark Publishing House, 2003; [1]

3. Bekmuratova U.B. abstract on the topic "The use of innovative technologies in teaching a foreign language." Tashkent 2012 [2]
4. Johnson, K.E. Sociocultural turn and its challenges for second language teacher education //TESOLQuarterly., London., 2006 [3] 4. www.library.uz [4]